

A Study of Job Satisfaction of School Teachers in Relation to Government and Private Schools of District Sangrur State Punjab (India)

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Abstract

In the present study the researcher investigated the level of job satisfaction among the private and government school teachers. Total 140 teachers, 70 from the government and 70 private schools were taken from Sangrur District. Job satisfaction scale developed by Minnesota was used to measure job satisfaction. To test the hypothesis 't'-test was used. Results showed that there was a significant difference between the job satisfaction of government and private school teachers. Furthermore, it was revealed that there was no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of male and female teachers.

Key Words: Job satisfaction, Government School Teachers and Private school Teachers.

Introduction

Job satisfaction is the positive and negative feelings of an employee towards his job or it is the amount of happiness connected with the job. Therefore, job satisfaction is one of the most widely spread researched topics in the field of organisational psychology .

According to Locke - 'job satisfaction is the positive and enjoyable feeling that results from the evaluation of one's job or job experience'.

'Teaching is the profession which teaches all of the other professions' the quotation is a fact showing that Teachers are the pillars of every nation. Teachers play an important part in developing the knowledge and skills of students at every level. Mathur (2002) said that "No system of education, no syllabus, methodology, no text books can rise above the level of its teachers. If a country wants to have quality education it must have quality teachers". Job satisfaction is an essential part of any progressive institution to be developed. Job Satisfaction leads to better performance on teachers' part.

Objectives

1. To study the job satisfaction of government and private school teachers.
2. To study the job satisfaction of teachers with respect to gender.

Hypotheses

- H1:** There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of private and government school teachers.
- H2:** There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of school teachers with respect to their gender.

Sample

The sample of the study consisted of the teachers working in government and private schools of Sangrur District of Punjab State(India). A sample of 140 teachers consisting of 70 private school teachers (35 male and 35 female) and 70 government school teachers(35 male and 35 female) was taken into consideration.

Tools

Job satisfaction scale developed by Minnesota 1967 was used to measure job satisfaction. To test the hypothesis 't' test was used.

Limitations of the study

- The present study is based on data collected from the Private and Govt schools of Sangrur district only.
- This study has limited sample size
- Some of the replies from the respondents may be biased

Analysis of Data

Hypothesis-1

	N	Mean	S.D	t value	Level of significance
Private School Teachers	70	13.25	7.26	6.55	0.05
Govt School Teachers	70	17.75	9.13		

Tabulated Value $t = 1.98$ at $df = 138$ at 0.05 level of significance

Conclusion

Since calculated value is 6.55 while tabulated value is 1.98 at $df = 138$ at 0.05 level of significance i.e Calculated value is $>$ tabulated Value which shows that there is significant difference between the job satisfaction of Govt. and Private School teachers. Therefore hypothesis 1 is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

	N	Mean	standard Deviation	t-value	Level of Significance
Males	70	18.14	12.4	0.502	0.05
Females	70	19.23	13.3		

Tabulated Value $t=1.98$ at $df= 138$ at 0.05 level of significance

Conclusion

Since calculated value is 0.502 while tabulated value is 1.98 at $df = 138$ at 0.05 level of significance i.e Calculated value is $<$ tabulated Value which shows that there is no significance difference between the job satisfaction of male and female teachers. Therefore hypothesis 2 is accepted.

References

- **Ahmed, Raheem, and Jamal(2003)** conducted a study on job satisfaction of 236 teachers in secondary school. It was observed that the female teachers are highly satisfied when compared to

the male teachers. The teachers working in the government school showed higher satisfaction than the teachers working in the private schools.

- **Gupta and Sahu(2009)** conducted a study on job satisfaction. It deals with the relationship of job satisfaction with the organisational stress and place of control on vocational teachers. The results revealed that there is no significant gender difference between organisational stress and place of control on vocational school teachers.
- **Agarwal(2004)** had done his study on job satisfaction of primary and secondary school teachers. The results obtained show that the experienced and married teachers of government schools are highly satisfied than the teachers of the private schools. It also revealed that age and marital status have no relationship with job satisfaction.

